

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B446
Date: 07 May 2009
Take Off: 04:54:28Z
Landing: 09:28:54Z
Flight Time 4h 34m 26s

Campaign: MEVEX Dust Flight 5
Operating Area: Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	Rob King	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
13	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
14	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
15	Observer	Dave Membury	Met Office	
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
CVI	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
SWS	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
Mini-LIDAR	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_051001_1hz.avi	faam-video-ffc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_061001_1hz.avi	faam-video-rfc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_051004_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_071001_1hz.avi	faam-video-rfc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_061004_1hz.avi	faam-video-rfc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_071004_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_081001_1hz.avi	faam-video-rfc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_081004_1hz.avi	faam-video-rfc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_081004_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_091001_1hz.avi		faam-video-rfc_faam_20090507_r0_b446_091004_1hz.avi

B446 02:48:25-10:01:08

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

MEVEX – IASI Sortie – B446
Date: 7th May 2009
Mission Scientist: Dave Kindred

T/O OOMS: 05:00Z (09:00 local)
Land OOMS: 09:12Z (13:12 local)

Location: Central Oman low level area 3
 A: 21°30'N 56°00'E B: 20°45'N 56°15'E

Coordinating with IASI overpass at 05:54Z

Weather: Cloud free conditions, high aerosol loadings

Sortie Aim: To validate IASI retrievals and forecasts of moderate aerosol conditions.

Key Instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, AVAPS, Nephs

Sortie profile:

Item No.	Detail	Item time	Running time	Local time
0	Perform pirouette before take-off			
1	Take off OOMS		05:00:00	09:00:00
2	Transit to operating area at FL260	00:40:00	05:40:00	09:40:00
3	Fly 2 straight and level runs at FL260 between points A and B, dropping 2 sondes on each run	00:20:00	06:00:00	10:00:00
4	Profile descent, from A to B, to FL150 or other suitable level	00:10:00	06:10:00	10:10:00
5	2 Straight and level runs at FL150	00:30:00	06:40:00	10:40:00
6	Profile descent to 8000ft or other suitable level	00:07:00	06:47:00	10:47:00
7	Continue straight and level run at 8000ft to A	00:10:00	06:57:00	10:57:00
8	Straight and level run at 8000ft A to B	00:15:00	07:12:00	11:12:00
9	Profile descent to 1000ft	00:10:00	07:22:00	11:22:00
10	Continue straight and level run at 1000ft to A	00:05:00	07:27:00	11:27:00
11	Perform 3 SLRs at 1000ft to arrive back at B	00:45:00	08:12:00	12:12:00
12	Profile ascent to transit alt between B and A	00:20:00	08:32:00	12:32:00
13	Transit back to OOMS	00:40:00	09:12:00	13:12:00
14	Perform pirouette after landing			
	Total sortie time		04:12:00	04:12:00

B446 07/05/09 AREA 3 (Central/W Oman)

MEVEX: IASI RETRIEVAL/MODEL FORECAST VERIFICATION OF MODERATE TO HIGH AEROSOL CONDITIONS

A very successful flight (4h 55m), encountering some high dust/aerosol loadings with significant vertical and horizontal structure. Maximum nephelometer values up to about 1150 (blue wavelength) to 1250 (green) to 1350 (red) per metre measured, with good separation between wavelengths seen, notably during the 4 runs at FL 130. Four dropsondes were launched close to the IASI satellite overpass time of 0554z, all giving good met & wind data. From resulting Tephigram plots, and guided by concurrent Lidar display information, 3 discrete levels were (correctly) selected and flown for maximum aerosol/dust content (FL180, FL130 and FL 090), with the mid (FL130) level constituting a significant 'dust event' (mainly small sized dust particles as seen by the PCASP). Very few instrument faults encountered, and weather conditions above aerosol top (~FL200) were generally clear, with ocnl patches of thin Ci present. This sortie should provide an excellent dataset, especially with the coherent Lidar/Neph/PCASP and Tephi information for model dust forecast verification, and wealth of thermodynamic & radiative measurements data for satellite retrieval/calibration (+ filter samples taken in the longer runs by visiting scientist, Anne Klaver).

After ground pirouette manoeuvre (0446 - 0449z) pre T/O (0454z), the following were flown:

1. Climb out of Muscat to FL260, and transit to operating area (working with ground points A [21 deg 30 min N; 56 deg 00 min E] and B [20 deg 45 min N; 56 deg 15 min E]). Very distinct & well-defined dust layer noted at FL130 heating out from Muscat.
2. Perform, at FL260, runs 1.1 (A-B) and 1.2 (B-A), dropping 4 sondes (054105z; 054417z; 055633z; and 055958z), equally spaced along line A-B.
3. Profile (P1), at 1000 ft/min, A-B, from FL260 to FL170 (just below likely chosen layer to be worked), climbing to FL180 to make run 2.1 (B-A), heading NNW.
4. Profile (P2), at 1000 ft/min, (A-B), FL180 to FL120, then climb to FL130 (P3) to work this thickest aerosol/dust layer, run 4.1, heading SSE, extending beyond point B, and returning as run 4.2 (extended B to A), heading NNW. Thicker aerosol to N of these runs noted; neph values between about 500 and 1350 per metre.
5. Profile (P4) descent from FL130 to FL080, then climb to FL090 to work this level, A-B, run 5.1, heading SSE; and run 5.2, B-A, heading NNW. Neph values generally 150 – 300 per metre along run, again with good horizontal structure (thicker to N).
6. Profile (P5), descent, FL090 to 1200 ft (minimum permitted altitude), at 1000 ft/min (but 500 ft/min below 3000 ft), A towards B, heading SSE, then reciprocal towards A from 4000 ft.
7. Dog-leg run pattern, at MPA -1200 ft, run 6.1, heading E from A (5 mins) then run 6.2 into sun (average heading 200 deg) for 10 mins to characterise surface, then run 6.3, heading W, (5 mins). Neph values about 150 per metre at this level on these runs.

8. Profile (P6), 1000 ft/min, from 1200 ft up to FL130, heading back towards B, then turning B-A track. Perform 2 MORE runs at this interesting (high dust loading) level: run 7.1, heading NNW towards A, and run 7.2, heading SSE towards B. Maximum levels of dust scattering from Neph on B446 seen along these runs (up to 1350 per metre).
9. Finally, profile (P6) was completed, FL130 to FL190 within operational area, then return transit to Muscat, landing at 0949z, finishing with a pirouette manoeuvre, 0951 – 0954z.

Instruments: The CPC was deemed u/s and taken off pre-flight. The medium wavelength camera (45 deg) needed cooling once airborne (with a high level transit) to become serviceable. FWVS worked well during the flight, but has a new controller (with new integration time) fitted. Otherwise few instrument problems.

Met: Winds generally NNW'ly to NNE'ly, light to moderate. Skies were mainly clear, apart from some small patches of Ci, (max 2/8 during sortie), mostly well to North.

DRK
08/05/2009

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B-446** Date **7-5-09** Name **DK** Page **2** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0539		FL260	135°		Nearly in operating area, Winds 050°/12kt.
0540		Man aerosol			
					level tracks now more like 10000' (3000m) in this area
054105	START R1.1 / Deploy #1	FL260 (25.9141)	154°		Deploy #1 released (run A → B) Some tracks good info. MAN coincident EXT overlpass WILL BE on Run 1.2 (S → X)
054417	Deploy #2	FL260	161°	26.12 N 86.00 W	Deploy #2 released.
055002					O/H Pt B
055113	END R1.1	FL260		→	Slow 5° turn (false sides) END R1.1 before starting R1.2.
055316				→	Turning slightly steeper L now.
055518	START R1.2	FL260			Start Run 1.2 SE of Pt B
055633	Deploy #3	FL260			O/H Pt B.
055938	Deploy #4	FL260			LAST SATE Dropped.
	FIRST LAYER				To be worked ~ 17-18000' (FRONT LIDAR & T/Φ's) Deploy #1 & 2.
060600	END R1.2	FL260			At Pt A turning ↓ slowly for releases.
060800					Tightening ↓ turn before 1st profile to FL170
061025					LAST SATE now on ground - ALL GOOD DATA
061124	START P1	FL260	164°		Profile descent A → B, 1000'/min to FL170 & decide on 1st run ht
		FL200			Start of alt changes on next
062039	END P1	FL170			Higher aerosol @ FL180 from LIDAR So will make this 1st run.

Mission Scientist's Log

13000'
5000' 1500'
8000'
3200' 120'

Flight No **B.446** Date **7-5-05** Name **DEK** Page **3** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
062409	2-1	FL180	326°		Run B → A (backwards) Visually in v Top of Aerosol layer.
062527	2	FL180	345°		
0633					Wind 020°/16 kt. TR 1/8 Ci to H. end of this Run & well to part of A/B.
063546	END R2.1	FL180	345°		Turn
063922	START P2	FL180	166°		START P2 ↓ FL120. [1007 Regional Aerosol]
064525	END D2	FL120			
064621	START P2				FL120 ↑ FL130 To by in the next aerosol layer (LIDAR/NEPH)
064721	END P3/START R4.1	FL130	160°		NEPH values ~400 m
0650		FL130			NEPH values mainly 500-600 m
~ 065100					[This Aerosol layer later ~500' lower than next] Passing Pt B. Red aerosol BLUE [Aerosol thicker this end of run visually]
065329	END F.1	FL130			Turning ↓ & preparing for R4.2, Extended B → A
065635	START R4.2	FL130	353°		Just a small particles (DASP)
~ 070530					NEPH values rising rapidly (>1000 m ⁻¹) To H end of run. (Still good R/G/B sep ² on NEPH)
~ 071030					NEPH Red only to ~800 m ⁻¹ now towards A
071126	END R4.2	FL130			Wind 053°/16 kt. END Run 14 V. Thick Aerosol / EXTENDED
					Longer than descending to next interesting Aerosol / dust layer expected at 8000-9000'.
071507	P4.1	FL130 FL080	171°		Start P4 to next Aerosol layer

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.446** Date **7-5-09** Name **DK** Page **4** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
071618					o/H 'A' Pt.
071625		DET HALT		Big Peak at ~12000' (1100-1200 m ⁻¹)	
071818		PASSING FL100		} VISUALLY V. THICK ACROSS:	CO jump passing thro thin layer here
072035	END P24	FL080	162°		} Best ends for dust / aerosol at FL090 (9000') & climb to this level & head towards B.
072215	START RS.1	FL090	160°		
0723					Depth ~ 300 m ⁻¹ .
0727					o/H 'B', extend this run by 3 mins for extra filter sampling time.
0729					Depth values 180-200 m ⁻¹ (thinner this end).
073018	END RS.1	FL090			Turning ↗ & will reexit leg AT THIS HEIGHT FOR DUST / AEROSOL
073224	START RS.2	FL090	314°		
0742					Lower values of depth confirmed AT 'B' end of run (150-200 m ⁻¹) of ~300 m ⁻¹ average [FANTASTIC STRUCTURE IN DEPTH]
074722	END S.2	FL090	165°		END RUN AT FL090.
075019	START PS	FL090 ↓	1300'		} Profile ↓ 2000' / min for low level runs (Daggeleg) wind 355 / 6 kt.
075430					
075542	PS Interrupt	4000'			Turning ↗ onto racetrack towards A
075712	Resume PS ↓	4000' ↓			1000' / min
075810		3000'			Reduce to 500' / min descent O ₃ ↑ large increase at ~2700'.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.746** Date **7-5-09** Name **DEK** Page **5** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
080138	END P5	1200'			Turning ↷ all way round onto 090° for 1 st part of dogleg run.
080449	START R6.1	1200'	094°		START 1 st dogleg run (of 3)
080939	END R6.1	1200'			→
081026	START R6.2	1200'	200°		INTO SW Run (200°).
081330					MAIN PIPELINE UNDER A/C NOW,
0816					AERIAL CAST Still Q. HIGH (Nephel 150 m^{-1}) 0.4 CDP ; 600 P/ASP.
					[A. Pt change on descent v. sharp change coming down to 1200'; steady at 1200' runs]
082025	END R6.2	1200'			END INTO SW Run.
082107	START R6.3	1200'	270°		Start last leg (of 3) of low-level dog legs
082609	END R6.3	1200'			[NEPH VALUES $\sim 150 \text{ m}^{-1}$ AT LOW LEVELS]
082731	START P6	1200'	098°		1000'/min. Heading back to Point B.
	TURN P6				Turn ↷ to head back to P+A.
					MINIMUM NEPH AT ABOUT 11000' (small dip)
					BUT $\nearrow$ VALUES OF NEPH 12,000'
083959	END P6/ START R7.1	13000'	346°		Holding PC & WILL PERFORM 2 MORE RUNS (7.1/7.2) IN THICKEST SWT / NEPH
084119					NEPH VALUES SLOWLY RISING HERE AS APPROACH P+A TO $\sim 1000 \text{ m}^{-1}$.
					AERIAL, layer
					LIGHT SEEING LAYER $\sim 3000'$ ($< 1000 \text{ m}$) below. descending below vs.
084553	END R7.1	13000'			V. HIGH NEPH VALUES NEAR P+A (up to $\sim 1350 \text{ m}^{-1}$ MAX)
					Turning ↷ onto reciprocal at A & returning for final run A→B at this (interesting dust) level.

Mission Scientist's Log

ETA
0950
(~35/40 min
extra)

Flight No **B-446** Date **7-5-09** Name **DK** Page **6** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
084655	Run 7.2	13000'	154°		Finish Run A → B (10 minutes)
0852.					CDP 7cc / Aerosol ~ 400 (Persp) Layers (Small dust)
		Max Height	Views		1350 Red 1250 green 1150 BLUE
		Start on Run			
		Layer beneath us (~1200 m)			becoming ventilar as head South
085848	END P7.2	13000'	152°		END LAST AEROSOL / DUST LAYER RUN
0800	Restart P6 (wind)	13000'	309°		Profile B → A climbing 1000' min
0903		16000'			now above most of aerosol (visually)
090508	P6 ↑	18000'	036°		031° / 12kt A/C restricted to FL190 in P6 ↑
					⇒ no problem as above interesting dust layers
090620	END P6	15000'	032°		END of PROFILE ASCENT, LRTB, ETA 0943
0949 0454				→	Landed MUSCET
04155					
0951(2)			180°		Start PIRouette AT MUSCET.
0954.			180°		END PIRouette
	(Blakes T. Blocks Shadow)				

B446-#mevexViRClog.txt

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[2009/0*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 07/05/2009 05:20:53
[2009/05/07 05:20] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/07 05:21] [FAAMOpsDetach] hiya
[2009/05/07 05:23] <FAAM_flt_man> wot ho
[2009/05/07 05:23] <FAAM_flt_man> just sent u a satcom c
[2009/05/07 05:24] [FAAMOpsDetach] hot woe!
[2009/05/07 05:24] [FAAMOpsDetach] ok will have a ganda
[2009/05/07 05:24] <FAAM_flt_man> Neph 1450 m-1 in layer at fl135
[2009/05/07 05:27] *** MetODaveP (~dfpollard@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/07 05:27] <MetODaveP> Are those loadings consistant throught the whole profile?
[2009/05/07 05:29] <FAAM_flt_man> lidar reports strong dust layer still present below us, currently
    at 21 42N 56 45E
[2009/05/07 05:30] <FAAM_flt_man> Layer present between FL110 and FL150, peaking at FL135 (1450 m-
    1)
[2009/05/07 05:32] <FAAM_flt_man> Lidar reports layer getting thicker as heading S. Dropping first
    sonde in approx 8 mins
[2009/05/07 05:33] <MetODaveP> Thats an AOD of ~0.9 just for that layer!
[2009/05/07 05:34] <FAAM_flt_man> nice
[2009/05/07 06:08] [FAAMOpsDetach] was lower shims fitted this morning?
[2009/05/07 06:10] <FAAM_flt_man> It was. In other news, MARSS falls over pre-flight, PCASP is
    noisy pre-flight and CPC fails to make the grade.
[2009/05/07 06:14] [FAAMOpsDetach] okay. Phil is quite concerned that old PCASP isn't tinkered
    with until endex ie it should be calibrated before any changes made
[2009/05/07 06:14] [FAAMOpsDetach] is marss working now?
[2009/05/07 06:33] *** Server connection lost
[2009/05/07 06:35] [FAAMOpsDetach] testing
[2009/05/07 06:39] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/07 06:39] [FAAMOpsDetach] how now?
[2009/05/07 06:40] <FAAM_flt_man> profiling down to FL130 looking for dust layer
[2009/05/07 06:41] [FAAMOpsDetach] is marss okay now?
[2009/05/07 06:42] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, MARSS IS OK
[2009/05/07 06:51] <FAAM_flt_man> no intercom probs either
[2009/05/07 06:55] [FAAMOpsDetach] good, good
[2009/05/07 06:55] [FAAMOpsDetach] over
[2009/05/07 06:56] <FAAM_flt_man> in dust layer, FL130, at point B, three distinct signals from the
    neph, blue = 350, green = 380, red = 410
[2009/05/07 07:00] [FAAMOpsDetach] are you flying inverted?
[2009/05/07 07:01] <FAAM_flt_man> nope
[2009/05/07 07:38] <FAAM_flt_man> Martyn requires no extra time for fault rectification
[2009/05/07 07:49] [FAAMOpsDetach] Okay, I'll pass on to Ops 'n Engs
[2009/05/07 07:58] <FAAM_flt_man> what's the word for tomorrow?
[2009/05/07 08:01] [FAAMOpsDetach] B447 t/o 0835L, Dave P flying, Dave K grounding, MS FM, SCD desk
    duties, otherwise same science crew
[2009/05/07 08:02] [FAAMOpsDetach] can you check if Dave M plans to fly tomorrow?
[2009/05/07 08:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] hello ho
[2009/05/07 08:25] <FAAM_flt_man> Dave M will be a ground-hog
[2009/05/07 08:29] [FAAMOpsDetach] okay
[2009/05/07 08:29] [FAAMOpsDetach] any more high dust loadings / scattering
[2009/05/07 08:31] <FAAM_flt_man> Ys, dusty flight all round really. High loadings e.g. 1000 m-1 in
    layer at FL130 which varied S (low) to N (high) on the A - B run.
[2009/05/07 08:32] <FAAM_flt_man> several sublayers also present
[2009/05/07 08:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] excellent
[2009/05/07 08:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] does that mean the eta has slipped?
[2009/05/07 08:34] <MetODaveP> Excellent, should keep some people in Exeter happy.
[2009/05/07 08:37] <FAAM_flt_man> not sure yet
[2009/05/07 08:41] <FAAM_flt_man> gone back to FL130 near pt A, Nph approx 1100 m-1 at present
[2009/05/07 08:43] <FAAM_flt_man> 1300
[2009/05/07 08:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] confirm eta 1300L?
[2009/05/07 08:45] <FAAM_flt_man> 1300m neph-1 reading on t
[2009/05/07 08:46] <FAAM_flt_man> Krappy ceyboard.... 1300m-1 reading on the neph
[2009/05/07 08:47] [FAAMOpsDetach] okay,
[2009/05/07 08:54] <FAAM_flt_man> ETA 0950....ETA 0950.....ETA 0950
[2009/05/07 08:58] [FAAMOpsDetach] copy noted understood over
[2009/05/07 09:04] [FAAMOpsDetach] Phil and Doug on way to airport, lunch looming
[2009/05/07 09:05] <FAAM_flt_man> wot to do?
[2009/05/07 09:06] [FAAMOpsDetach] CPC checking and packup bits
[2009/05/07 09:21] [FAAMOpsDetach] any requests before I go to lunch?
[2009/05/07 09:25] <FAAM_flt_man> no
[2009/05/07 09:29] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.3) has quit IRC
[2009/05/07 09:34] *** MetODaveP (~dfpollard@85.154.2.202) has quit IRC
*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 07/05/2009 09:39:59
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Cloud Physics Flight Log B446

Date: 7/05/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 03:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?												No
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.47	Ref V (~3):	2.91	Vref (>7):	unknown	El#1 V (>1):	-1.5	Ref V:	3.5	Comms?	No
	Sample flow	1.16			Flow (~1):	0.62	El#32 V (>1):	-1.5				
	Sheath flow	14.7			Pressure:	1007						
					Temp (NDIT)	34						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
													PCASP ch1 noise from t/o
													Heaters on
05:03:00	FL135	10	3	400	1	350	0.06				23		Dust layer 1000' thick
05:15:00	FL260												Old PCASP ch2 noise, ch3 OK
05:41:10	FL260												Start Run 1.1
05:42:00				40	0.3	Noise					24		
05:44:00				40	0.3	Noise							
05:46:00				40	0.3	Noise	Ch3 ok						
05:48:00				40	0.3	Noise							
05:50:00				40	0.3	Noise							
05:51:13													End of Run
05:55:21	FL260												Start Run 1.2
05:56:00				40	0.3	Noise							
05:58:00				40	0.3	Noise							
06:00:00				40	0.3	Noise					25		
06:02:00				40	0.3	Noise							
06:04:00				40	0.3	Noise							
06:06:01													End of Run
06:11:25	FL260			40	0.3	Noise							Start Profile 1
06:12:33	FL250			40	0.3	Noise							
06:13:37	FL240			40	0.3	Noise							
06:14:38	FL230			40	0.3	Noise							
06:15:38	FL220			40	0.3	Noise							

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
06:16:42	FL210			45	0.3	Noise							
06:17:45	FL200			80	0.3	Noise							
06:18:44	FL190			80	0.3	Noise							
06:19:41	FL180			180	0.3	Noise							
06:20:37	FL170			100	0.3	Noise							End of Profile
06:24:11	FL180												Start Run 2.1
06:25:00		0.1	2	150	1	120					26		Ch1 noise still high but ch2 ok, so no mean r
06:27:00		0.1	2	150	1	90							
06:29:00		0.1	2	150	1	90							
06:31:00		0.1	2	150	1	85							
06:33:00		0.1	2	150	1	75							
06:35:00		0.1	2	150	1	80							
06:35:48													End of Run
0639:24	FL180	0.1	2	150	1	60							Start Profile 2
06:40:32	FL170			150	1	110							
06:41:34	FL160	0.1	2	200	1	160							
06:42:36	FL150	0.1	2	200	1	180							
06:43:36	FL140	1	6	300	1	300							
06:44:32	FL130	3	10	400	2	430					32		
06:45:28	FL120	3	10	350	2	350					35		End of Profile & Start run 3.1
06:46:31	FL120												End of Run & Start Profile 3
06:47:28	FL130												End of Profile & Start Run 4.1
06:48:00		2.5	10	400	2	340					38		
06:50:00		3	10	350	2	300					42		
06:52:00		3.5	10	350	2	270					48		
06:53:25													End of Run
06:56:39	FL130												Start Run 4.2
06:57:00		1.5	10	350	2	250					54		
06:59:00		3.5	10	500	2	330					59		
07:01:00		3.5	10	450	2	320					61		
07:03:00		2.5	10	450	2	320							
07:05:00		1.5	10	400	2	250					64		
07:07:00		2	10	450	2	350					66		
07:09:00		5	10	550	2	450					72		
07:11:00		2.5	10	500	2	330					77		
07:11:30													End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
07:15:09	FL130	3	10	500	2	450					83		Start Profile 4
07:16:29	FL120	4	10	500	2	550					86		
07:17:32	FL110	4	10	700	2	720					88		
07:18:25	FL100	4	10	600	2	650							
07:19:30	FL090	1.5	10	550	2	500					89		
07:20:37	FL080	1	10	500	2	450					90		End of Profile
07:22:22	FL090												Start Run 5.1
07:23:00		1.5	10	450	2	400					92		
07:25:00		1.5	10	500	2	360					95		
07:27:00		1.5	10	500	2	350					97		Heaters off except old pcasp
07:29:00		1.5	10	450	2	400					98		
07:30:17													End of Run
07:32:15	FL090												Start Run 5.2
07:33:00		0.8	10	450	2	400					99		
07:35:00		1	10	450	2	380					101		
07:37:00		1.2	10	400	2	430					102		
07:39:00		1.4	10	400	2	420					104		
07:41:00		1.8	12	420	2	430					106		
07:43:00		1.6	12	450	2	475					107		
07:45:00		1.4	12	420	2	540					109		
07:47:00		1.8	10	425	2	600					111		
07:47:26													End of Run
07:50:21	FL090												Start Profile 5
07:51:30	FL080	1.4	10	500	2	780					115		Ch2 noise?
07:52:36	FL070	1	10	500	2	550							
07:53:51	FL060	1	10	500	2	600					116		Old pcasp heater off
07:54:50	FL050	1	10	450	2	750					117		CH2 noise?
07:55:51	FL040	1	10	425	2	800							
07:58:18	FL030	0.5	5	150	1.5	550					118		
08:00:11	FL020	0.6	7	600	2	1000					119		
08:01:38	1000'												End of profile
08:04:41	1000'	0.5	7	600	2	750					121		Start Run 6.1
08:05:00													
08:07:00		0.5	7	650	2	650			0.5				
08:09:00		0.5	7	700	2	700			0.5		122		
0809:42													End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
08:10:30	1000'												Start Run 6.2
08:11:00		0.5	7	700	2	620		1			123		
08:13:00		0.4	7	650	2	610		0.5			124		
08:15:00		0.5	7	600	2	700		0.5					
08:17:00		0.5	7	600	2	600		1			125		
08:19:00		0.4	7	600	2	700		0.5			126		
08:20:27													End of Run
08:21:10	1000'												Start Run 6.3
08:22:00		0.5	7	600	2	650		0.5			127		
08:24:00		0.3	7	600	2	610							
08:26:11													End of Run
08:27:28	1000'												Start Profile 6.1
08:28:12	FL020	0.3	7	600	2	530		0.5					
08:29:05	FL030	0.3	7	500	2	380		0.5			129		
08:29:55	FL040	0.4	7	400	2	330							
08:30:54	FL050	0.5	7	450	2	375		0.5			130		
08:31:50	FL060	0.5	7	450	2	400							Old pcasp heater on
08:32:44	FL070	0.6	7	500	2	375					131		
08:33:37	FL080	0.7	7	500	2	500					132		
08:35:50	FL090	0.8	7	500	2	280					133		
08:36:55	FL100	0.8	7	300	2	310							
08:37:44	FL110	0.2	7	400	2	450							
08:38:42	FL120	4	10	300	2	375							
08:39:58	FL130												End of profile & Start Run 7.1
08:40:00		4	10	300	2	750					137		Ch2 noise? Or just too high activity
08:42:00		5	10	400	2	750							Ch2 noise?
08:44:00		6	10	400	2	Noise					146		
08:45:53													End of Run
08:48:50	FL130												Start Run 7.2
08:49:00		5	10	400		Noise					157		
08:51:00		6	10	450		Noise					164		
08:53:00		7	10	400		Noise					168		
08:55:00		6	10	400		Noise					171		
08:57:00		4	10	350		Noise					173		
08:58:50													End of Run
09:00:15	FL130												Start Profile 6.2

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B446

Date:

07-05-2009

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B446-N35	----	----	Top					Blanks (FL 260)
Filters run1	B446-N36	----	----	Bottom					
Filters run 2	B446-N37	----	----	Top	06:24:37	06:35:25		93	FL 180 (Top of the dust layer)
Filters run 2	B446-N38	----	----	Bottom	06:24:37	06:35:25		89	
Filters run 3	B446-N39	----	----	Top	06:48:21	07:10:55		359	FL 131 Dust load varies during the sampling
Filters run 3	B446-N40	----	----	Bottom	06:48:21	07:10:55		328	
Filters run 4	B446-N41	----	----	Top	07:23:14	07:30:18		173	9100 ft
Filters run 4	B446-N42	----	----	Bottom	07:23:14	07:30:18		153	
Filters run 5	B446-N43	----	----	Top	08:10:24	08:20:05		430	140, 130 ft
Filters run 5	B446-N44	----	----	Bottom	08:10:24	08:20:05		404	

Flight:

B446

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H (VIRC):
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI (Inlet):
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B446
Date: 07 May 2009

Instruments

CPC – resurrection attempted pre-flight, but the CPC remains resolutely in-operable

Cloud Physics

SID3 not operated
old pcasp noisy pre-flight

CPC – reported CPC fault when green run button selected after take-off.

Nevezorov; failed sensor, not operated

MARSS – instrument failed pre-flight but recovered during flight

SWS/SHIMS - lower shims fitted pre-flight

SATCOM-H: mpds service good

GIN – serviceable

AMTG screen blanked although unit still operated

FWVS – integration oscillations on data but otherwise very good

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ARIES flight log

Flight:	B 446	page 1 of 3
Date: 07/MAY/09	Operator(s): S. ROGERS	Res: 1
Gain A: 2 B: 2		
Loc./Notes: MEXX: Dust.		

← Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0457	TAKE OFF						
05 05 15	FL158	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal. macro Cloud above + below Dust below
05 15 15	FL260	Nad/Zen	NZ	0	81	41	Nadir Zenith 30 sec
05 36 25	"	cal	CH	0	81	40	CH cal.
05 37 47	"	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
05 40 30	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal. Sande
05 41 52	"	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
05 43	"	60x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
05 43 40	"	60x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
05 44 29	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
05 45 51	"	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
05 49 53	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
05 53 24	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
05 54 45	"	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir 1A51 overlaps 0554 turn at start of Nadir sande.
05 58 55	"	cal	CH	0	82	41	CH cal.
06 00 22	"	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
06 04 31	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 20 45	NFL175	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 22 06	FL180	240x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir in turn
06 24 11	"	240x1	N	0	81	40	Nadir
06 26 13	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 28 -	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
06 29 08	"	120x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
06 30 28	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
06 32 31	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 34 13	"	240x1	N	0	80	41	Nadir
06 35 55	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 45 22	FL120	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 47 -	FL130	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 48 40	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
06 49 39	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith

ARIES flight log

Flight: B446 page 2 of 3

Date: _____ Operator(s): _____ Res: _____ Gain A: _____ B: _____

Loc./Notes: _____

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
06 51 50	FL130	240x1	N	0	81	40	Nadir
06 53 30	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 56 36	FL130	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
06 58 02	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	CH Zenith
06 59 12	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
07 01 25	"	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
07 02 36	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
07 03 59	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
07 06 18	"	240x1	Z	0			Zenith
07 09 50	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
		240x1	Z				
07 14 36	FL130	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
07 19 42	↓9000'	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
07 22 18	9000'	240x1	Z	0	81	42	CH cal.
07 24 50	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
07 25 55	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
07 27 18	"	240x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
07 28 00	"	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
07 30 01	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
07 30 28	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
07 32 32	9000'	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
07 33 51	"	360x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
07 36 55	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
07 38 11	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
07 39 45	"	360x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
07 42 49	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
07 44 10	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
07 45 39	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
07 47 24	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
08 01 26	1400'	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal Bumpy <i>Janis</i>
08 04 40		60x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 446

page 3 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Sht	HBB	CBB	Comments
08 05 27	B300	480 x 1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Bungy
08 08 52	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
	"	60 x 1	Z	0			Zenith
08 11 10	"	360 x 1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
08 14 10	"	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
08 15 32	"	60 x 1	Z	0			Zenith Still Bungy
08 16 27	"	360 x 1	N	0	81	43	Nadir I hope you damned
08 19 28	"	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal. Scientists appreciate the
08 21 08	"	60 x 1	Z	0	81	44	Zenith nausea we operators go
08 22 03	"	360 x 1	N	0	81	43	Nadir through to get this
08 25 06	"	cal	CH	0	81	44	CH cal. quality data for you!
08 39 -	FL130	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
08 41 18	"	240 x 1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith.
08 43 27	"	240 x 1	Z				
08 43 48	"	240 x 1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
08 45 53	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
08 48 45	FL130	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
08 50 06	"	240 x 1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
08 52 15	"	240 x 1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
08 54 37	"	240 x 1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
08 56 26	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
08 57 47	"	240 x 1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
08 07 26	FL190	NadirZen	NZ	0	81	41	nadir Zenith 30 seconds until 09 29.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	07/05/09	Flight	B446	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King	Campaign	MEVEX			
Departure	Arrival					

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	31°C	Ch 17	31°C	Ch18	31°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					0315
Initial target temperatures	Hot	307	Cold	307		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold			
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again						at time

D20090507_054109.1 081939323 none, none

SONDE DROP ①
054105#

D20090507_054438.2 082029193 none, none

Sonde DRof (2)

054417z

D20090507_055638.3 081939410 none, none

Se. de Del (3)

055633 #

D20090507_055942.4 082029214 none, none

Seide Deep (4)
055938 f.

New plot, same times

Flight B446 09:10:24

Heading 34 deg Speed 291 knots Height 19.0kft Press 485mb

Lat 21°30.0'N Long 56°24.0'E Wind 6 ms-1/ 3 deg

Temp -7.97C Dewpoint -21.21C

From 07:21:42 to now

2nd PAIR OF RUS
13000 FT. (FL130)
(V. Height JUST LOADING)

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	33024	secs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All
NEPH BLUE SP	14.92	m-1	<input type="checkbox"/>
NEPH GREEN SP	13.77	m-1	<input type="checkbox"/>
NEPH RED SP	12.32	m-1	<input type="checkbox"/>

Flight B446 09:10:43

Heading 34 deg Speed 293 knots Height 19.0kft Press 485mb
 Lat 21°30.0'N Long 56°24.0'E Wind 5 ms-1/ 5 deg
 Temp -8.05C Dewpoint -20.66C
 From 07:55:45 to now

PROFILE OUT
 OF AREA 3.
 (PG)

Current values		
+++++ STATIC PRESSURE	485.25	mb
----- DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-8.06	deg C
----- DEW POINT	-20.67	deg C

[Profile out
PG of Area -
Part 1]
(1200' → 13000'
FL130)

Flight B446 08:51:01

Heading 161 deg Speed 264 knots Height 13.1kft Press 614mb

Lat 21°24.0'N Long 56°0.0'E Wind 7 ms-1/ 58 deg

Temp 3.66C Dewpoint -4.97C

From 07:55:45 to now

Current values		
+++++ STATIC PRESSURE	614.61	mb
----- DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	3.67	deg C
----- DEW POINT	-4.98	deg C

Flight B446 07:28:49

Heading 158 deg Speed 257 knots Height 9.1kft Press 719mb

Lat 20°36.0'N Long 56°12.0'E Wind 7 ms-1/ 51 deg

Temp 13.59C Dewpoint -3.24C

From start to now

PRESSURE HT
 v
 NEPHS

	Current values		
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	2791.97	m
.....	NEPH BLUE SP	170.11	m-1
.....	NEPH GREEN SP	191.92	m-1
.....	NEPH RED SP	194.88	m-1

Flight B446 07:29:05

Heading 159 deg Speed 253 knots Height 9.1kft Press 719mb

Lat 20°36.0'N Long 56°12.0'E Wind 7 ms-1/ 51 deg

Temp 13.34C Dewpoint -2.62C

From start to now

~~SHMS~~ OUT of MUSCAT
 Profile FL260 ↘ FL080

Current values		
++++	STATIC PRESSURE	719.82 mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	13.35 deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-2.63 deg C

Flight B446 05:15:53

Heading 207 deg Speed 317 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 22°24.0'N Long 57°30.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 22 deg

Temp -24.83C Dewpoint -47.48C

From start to now

CLIMB
~~CLIMB~~ OUT FROM
 MUSCAT AFTER T/O

(EXCELLENT HIGH WIND
 Loading, THIN LAYER
 @ 7000 m
 ≈ 13000ft
 = FL130)

Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	7935	m
.....	NEPH BLUE SP	3.61	m-1
.....	NEPH GREEN SP	0.41	m-1
.....	NEPH RED SP	2.65	m-1

Flight B446 05:16:04

Heading 207 deg Speed 312 knots Height 25.9kft Press 360mb
 Lat 22°24.0'N Long 57°30.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 22 deg
 Temp -24.6C Dewpoint -49.53C
 From start to now

CLIMB
~~CLIMB~~ OUT FROM
 MUST
 AFTER T/O.

Current values		
STATIC PRESSURE	360.21	mb
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-24.61	deg C
DEW POINT	-49.54	deg C

EEEJ11 MSG 321 RGB 07 May 2009 1145 UTC

EEEJ41 MSG dust RGB 07 May 2009 1145 UTC

EIEJ51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 07 May 2009 1130 UTC

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 00Z on 7/05/2009

AOD T+006

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 00Z on 7/05/2009

Dust concentration (log3) T+006

Southern Asia CAM Cloud
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 00Z on 7/05/2009

Total Cloud Cover T+006

Oktas

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 12Z on 6/05/2009

AOD T+018

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 12Z on 6/05/2009

Dust concentration (log3) T+018

Southern Asia CAM Cloud
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 12Z on 6/05/2009

Total Cloud Cover T+018

Oktas

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Southern Asia CAM Horizontal Winds
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 12Z on 6/05/2009

700hPa Wind T+018

EIEJ51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 07 May 2009 0145 UTC

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 00Z on 6/05/2009

AOD T+030

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 00Z on 6/05/2009

Dust concentration (leg3) T+030

Southern Asia CAM Cloud
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 00Z on 6/05/2009

Total Cloud Cover T+030

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 12Z on 5/05/2009

AOD T+042

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 06Z on 7/05/2009, from 12Z on 5/05/2009

Dust concentration (leg3) T+042

